

Cheat sheet: submitting a final DMP

Do I need a final DMP?

You should check the funder requirements. For FWO, the final and updated DMP must be **submitted with the final report of the project** and submitted to FWO via the e-portal. The DMP will be checked by the evaluation panel during the **final evaluation** of the project. The final report will be considered as incomplete in the absence of a detailed DMP. It is always good practice to keep the DMP updated and to record your decisions in a final DMP.

What is different in the final DMP?

At this stage, your data management plan should list all the research materials used and produced during the project, and describe them comprehensively. It should focus on clearly describing the **preservation strategy** and indicating where data/materials and documentation are **accessible**, for whom are these accessible and under which conditions.

Research data summary

- The table listing research data or other research material used and/or generated during the project is **updated and complete**.
- For each research dataset or material, sufficient details are provided.
- Whenever existing/third-party data have been reused, this is clearly indicated.

? How much **granularity**? You should make at least different rows for data/materials that have been treated differently. Eg. published as distinct datasets, different preservation locations, confidential vs. non-confidential, etc.

💡 These details should **allow others to understand the data management approach adopted** for each dataset/material. For example: if you indicate any dataset as confidential, it should not be made open; if you have data that is too large to deposit externally, you may choose institutional infrastructure as your preservation medium.

💡 If the data is published online, indicate the DOI or other **persistent identifier** of the reused dataset(s). In any other cases, clarify how the data has been obtained and which type of agreement is in place with the data provider.

Ethical and legal issues

- A reference to **ethical approval** from the ethics commission is provided, when applicable

💡 To ensure clarity and coherence across the DMP, always **refer back to the dataset name or number as listed in the data summary section**. Datasets carrying ethical and/or legal implications should be presented either as individual items or in separate rows in the data summary table.

Personal data

- A reference to the **GDPR register** is provided, when applicable.
- Datasets containing personal data are clearly identified, and a **description of the processed personal data** is provided.

? **What details are relevant for data management?** What are the implications in terms of e.g. security measures, data sharing or preservation? For example: are you processing special categories of personal data and/or about vulnerable groups? Are you using any specific tools to collect and/or process these data? Are these GDPR-compliant?

Valorization of research

- Data or research materials that are subject to confidentiality due to valorization potential are clearly indicated.

💡 If a **patent** application has been submitted, indicate the patent application number.

Third-party agreements

- Data or research materials affected by third-party agreements are clearly indicated.
 - The third party is named, and a reference to the agreement or agreement location is provided.
 - Restrictions governed by these third-party agreements are briefly described and properly recorded in metadata and/or documentation.

💡 Common research situations where third-party agreements may apply are surveys conducted by a third-party or using a third-party tool, research using data from an industrial partner, multi-institutional projects with a collaboration agreement, etc.

? What are possible agreement clauses with **implications for data management**? Those related to data ownership, restrictions to (open) data sharing, confidentiality, on-site data processing, data retention and disposal, etc.

Intellectual property

- Other IP-related impacts on data or research materials not covered previously are indicated.
 - Any possible restrictions related to IP on the indicated research data or materials are clearly described.

💡 For example, when (re)using third-party data (including software) that was available online.

❓ Is there a license attached to the data? What is allowed by the license and under which conditions? Or, is the material copyrighted?

Metadata and documentation

- For each dataset (or research material) listed in the research summary section, the **approach for documentation** is described and the location of the documentation is indicated.
- For each research dataset or material deposited in a data repository, the **metadata standard** that has been used to make **data findable online** has been indicated.
- For datasets for which no metadata standard was used, the metadata elements created to make data easier to find and reuse are listed, and the location where this metadata is stored is provided.

💡 Preferably, **documentation is preserved or shared alongside with data**:

- Within a file package, e.g. readme file, protocols or standard operating procedures, questionnaire templates, informed consent template, lab, field or computational notebook, etc.
- With references to related publications or datasets, links to code (in GitHub), project website, etc. These can be provided in specific metadata fields offered by the data repository.

❓ Data repositories usually adhere to or are compatible with certain metadata standards. This information can often be found in the guidance or FAQs of the data repository.

Data storage & back-up

- Research data or materials that are still in active use are indicated, and the storage location and back-up measures are described.

💡 You may replicate the data summary table but, this time, using new columns to indicate whether data is preserved or not (and why), preservation location and preservation period.

Data preservation

- The research data or materials which have been preserved are indicated.
 - The **location** (institutional and/or external archive) and the **period** for preservation are specified.
- The **curation measures** implemented to preserve data in the long-term are detailed.
- For research data or materials that have not been preserved, a justification is provided.

❓ **Preserving is more than simply not deleting them.** Curation measures may entail: migrating files to open formats, relocating data to a more suitable location (e.g. institutional or external archive), managing access and write permissions, providing documentation (and metadata) together with data, etc.

❓ There can be good reasons for not preserving data or materials: data is easily reproducible (e.g. simulation data), legal or contractual obligations, data with direct identifiers, high costs vs. scientific relevance, etc. When data is not preserved, it is still recommended to keep documentation.

Data sharing

- The final selection of data or materials that have been shared is defined.
 - For each data or material, the chosen data repository (or any alternative sharing venue) is indicated, and the access level and reuse conditions (e.g. license) are specified.
 - A persistent identifier or a link is provided for each published dataset.
- For data that has not been published, describe future plans for sharing or justify why they cannot be shared.

💡 You may also replicate the data summary table here, with additional columns to provide information about the data repository, persistent identifiers, access and reuse conditions.

❓ There are legitimate reasons why not to share data. These should have been clearly indicated in the ethical and legal section of the DMP.